

DETECTION OF MULTIPLE POINT IMPACTS ACTING ON COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL PANELS

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SUMMARY

For the detection of multiple point impacts acting on composite structural panels, the impact locations and impact force histories are identified by adjusting modal coordinates to the measured ones which are determined from longitudinal strain responses. The validity of the detection is verified by comparing the identification results with the exact ones.

Keywords: Composite structural panel, Multiple point impacts, Detection, Impact location, Impact force history, Structural health monitoring

INTRODUCTION

It has attracted much attention to detecting impacts acting on composite structural panels, because the location and evolution of induced damage can be predicted. Tracy and Chang [1], Tajima et al. [2] and Hu et al. [3] studied the methods for identifying the location and force history of a single point impact on composite laminated plates. In those papers, the strain responses at certain points on the composite laminated plates were used as measured information. On the other hand, Sato et al. [4] and Onozaki and Sekine [5-7] have proposed the identification methods using acceleration responses at points on composite laminated plates.

Structural complexity of composite panel components leads to difficulties of the identification of locations and force histories of point impacts. Although there is a rather extensive literature on the detection of point impacts on composite laminated plates as previously mentioned, few investigations have been made into the detection of point impacts on composite structural panels, such as composite grid-stiffened panels and composite sandwich panels. Thus far, the detection has been examined for a single point impact on composite laminated panels with beam stiffeners [8], composite grid-stiffened panels [9] and composite sandwich panels [10, 11].

In this paper, we are concerned with the detection of multiple point impacts acting on composite structural panels. After examining the identification results of the location and force history of a single point impact on a rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel and a rectangular composite sandwich panel, the identification of the locations and force histories of multiple point impacts on the rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel and the rectangular composite sandwich panel is performed, and then we verify the validity of the detection of multiple point impacts.

MODELS OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL PANELS SUBJECTED TO MULTIPLE POINT IMPACTS

Fig. 1 shows rectangular composite structural panels subjected to multiple point impacts: (a) a composite isogrid-stiffened panel, (b) a composite sandwich panel. The multiple point impacts act transversely on the outer surface of the panels. The side lengths of panels are L and W . The thickness of panels is H , i.e., $H = h^s + h^s$ for the composite isogrid-stiffened panel and $H = 2h^f + h^c$ for the composite sandwich panel, where h^s is the thickness of skin panel, h^g the height of isogrid, h^f the thickness of face sheet and h^c the thickness of core. With regard to the boundary conditions, the rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel is simply supported on the four edges and the rectangular composite sandwich panel is clamped on the four edges.

METHOD FOR IDENTIFYING LOCATIONS AND FORCE HISTORIES OF MULTIPLE POINT IMPACTS

In the analysis, a three-dimensional finite element method is used. When the multiple point impacts are supposed to act expediently at nodes on the outer surface of the composite structural panels, the equation of motion governing the dynamic response of the

Fig. 1 Rectangular composite structural panels.

panels subjected to multiple point impacts is written in terms of modal coordinates as

$$\ddot{\xi}_i(t) + \omega_i^2 \xi_i(t) = -\boldsymbol{\phi}_i^T \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\eta}_p f_p(t) \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots) \quad (1)$$

where $\xi_i(t)$ is the i th modal coordinate, ω_i the angular frequency of the i th mode, $\boldsymbol{\phi}_i$ the i th mode shape vector, $\boldsymbol{\eta}_p$ the unit vector designating the freedom of the nodal force of p th point impact, $f_p(t)$ the force of the p th point impact, N_p the maximum number of coating multiple point impacts and t time. When ξ_i and $\dot{\xi}_i$ are set at $\xi_i(0) = \dot{\xi}_i(0) = 0$, the solution of Eq. (1) is given by

$$\xi_i(t) = -\boldsymbol{\phi}_i^T \int_0^t \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\eta}_p f_p(\tau) \frac{\sin\{\omega_i(t - \tau)\}}{\omega_i} d\tau \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots) \quad (2)$$

Time is divided into the same time intervals $t_j - t_{j-1} = \Delta t$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots$) where $t_0 = 0$. Moreover, $f_p(t)$ is approximated by the piecewise linear function, as follows:

$$f_p(t) = f_p(t_{j-1}) + \frac{f_p(t_{j-1} + \Delta t) - f_p(t_{j-1})}{\Delta t} (t - t_{j-1}) \quad \text{in } 0 \leq t - t_{j-1} \leq \Delta t \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots) \quad (3)$$

where $f_p(t_0)$ is zero. Substituting Eq. (3) into Eq. (2), we obtain

$$\xi_i(t_k) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_i^T \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\eta}_p a_i(j, k) f_p(t_j) \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots; k = 1, 2, \dots) \quad (4)$$

where

$$a_i(j, k) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{\omega_i^2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{\sin(\omega_i \Delta t)}{\omega_i \Delta t} \right\} & (j = k) \\ \frac{2}{\omega_i^3 \Delta t} \sin\{\omega_i(k - j)\Delta t\} \{\cos(\omega_i \Delta t) - 1\} & (j < k) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In order to identify the locations and force histories of multiple point impacts, we use the measured longitudinal strains at strain measurement positions on the free edge side of isogrid for the composite isogrid-stiffened panel and the inner surface of bottom face sheet for the composite sandwich panel. Using the first M modal coordinates, the longitudinal strain $\varepsilon_L(t)$ at the strain measurement positions is given by

$$\varepsilon_L(t) = \boldsymbol{\zeta}^T \mathbf{T} \mathbf{B} \sum_{i=1}^M \xi_i(t) \boldsymbol{\phi}_i^{(e)} \quad (6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ is the unit vector which designates the normal strain component in the direction of the longitudinal strain, \mathbf{T} the transformation matrix, \mathbf{B} the strain-displacement matrix and $\boldsymbol{\phi}_i^{(e)}$ the i th mode shape vector of element.

Let the total number of the strain measurement positions be $N_R (< M)$, and it is supposed that a longitudinal strain is measured at each of the strain measurement positions. By use of Eq. (6), the longitudinal strains at the strain measurement positions

Q_r ($r = 1, 2, \dots, N_R$) are expressed as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_L = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\Phi \boldsymbol{\xi} + \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_\Phi \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_L = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{L1} & \varepsilon_{L2} & \cdots & \varepsilon_{LN_R} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (8)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_1^T \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{B}_1 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{1,1}^{(e)} & \zeta_1^T \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{B}_1 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{1,2}^{(e)} & \cdots & \zeta_1^T \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{B}_1 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{1,N_R}^{(e)} \\ \zeta_2^T \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{B}_2 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{2,1}^{(e)} & \zeta_2^T \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{B}_2 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{2,2}^{(e)} & \cdots & \zeta_2^T \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{B}_2 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{2,N_R}^{(e)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ \zeta_{N_R}^T \mathbf{T}_{N_R} \mathbf{B}_{N_R} \boldsymbol{\phi}_{N_R,1}^{(e)} & \zeta_{N_R}^T \mathbf{T}_{N_R} \mathbf{B}_{N_R} \boldsymbol{\phi}_{N_R,2}^{(e)} & \cdots & \zeta_{N_R}^T \mathbf{T}_{N_R} \mathbf{B}_{N_R} \boldsymbol{\phi}_{N_R,N_R}^{(e)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \zeta_1^T \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{B}_1 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{1,N_R+1}^{(e)} & \zeta_1^T \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{B}_1 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{1,N_R+2}^{(e)} & \cdots & \zeta_1^T \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{B}_1 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{1,M}^{(e)} \\ \zeta_2^T \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{B}_2 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{2,N_R+1}^{(e)} & \zeta_2^T \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{B}_2 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{2,N_R+2}^{(e)} & \cdots & \zeta_2^T \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{B}_2 \boldsymbol{\phi}_{2,M}^{(e)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ \zeta_{N_R}^T \mathbf{T}_{N_R} \mathbf{B}_{N_R} \boldsymbol{\phi}_{N_R,N_R+1}^{(e)} & \zeta_{N_R}^T \mathbf{T}_{N_R} \mathbf{B}_{N_R} \boldsymbol{\phi}_{N_R,N_R+2}^{(e)} & \cdots & \zeta_{N_R}^T \mathbf{T}_{N_R} \mathbf{B}_{N_R} \boldsymbol{\phi}_{N_R,M}^{(e)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\xi} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1 & \xi_2 & \cdots & \xi_{N_R} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_{N_R+1} & \xi_{N_R+2} & \cdots & \xi_M \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (12)$$

Here, it is noted that the subscript refers to the quantity corresponding to a strain measurement position or a mode.

Following the work by Sun et al. [12], the locations of the strain measurement positions Q_r ($r = 1, 2, \dots, N_R$) are determined by minimizing the error in the first N_R modal coordinates due to the $M - N_R$ higher order modal coordinates. Then, the following optimization problem is set up.

$$\text{Minimize : } \lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{A}_{sp}) \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Design variables : } Q_r, \mathbf{T}_r \quad (r = 1, 2, \dots, N_R)$$

where λ_{\max} is the maximum eigenvalue of the matrix \mathbf{A}_{sp} , i.e.

$$\mathbf{A}_{sp} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_\Phi^T (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\Phi^{-1})^T \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\Phi^{-1} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_\Phi \quad (14)$$

The locations and force histories of multiple point impacts are identified in such a manner that the modal coordinates $\xi_i(t_k)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N_R; k = 1, 2, \dots, J$) given by Eq. (4) are adjusted to the measured modal coordinates $\xi_i^*(t_k)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N_R; k = 1, 2, \dots, J$), where J is the total number of the time intervals. The measured modal coordinates $\xi_i^*(t_k)$ at each time t_k are determined by substituting the measured longitudinal strains $\varepsilon_{Lr}^*(t_k)$ ($r = 1, 2, \dots, N_R$) into $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_L$ in Eq. (7) and solving the simultaneous linear algebraic equations of $\xi_i(t_k)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N_R$) after the $M - N_R$ higher order modal coordinates $\xi_i(t_k)$ ($i = N_R + 1, N_R + 2, \dots, M$) are truncated. If the distance between the coacting point impacts is assumed to be longer than d , i.e., the coacting point impacts

within the distance d are regarded as one point impact, the identification problem reduces to the optimization problem which is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Minimize : } E &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_R} \left\| \bar{\xi}_i^* - \sum_{p=1}^{N_P} \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{F}_{ip} \right\|^2 + w \sum_{\substack{p,q=1 \\ p \neq q}}^{N_P} \{H(d_{pq}) - H(d_{pq} - d)\} \\
\text{Subject to : } f_p(t_j) &\geq 0 \quad (p = 1, 2, \dots, N_P; j = 1, 2, \dots, J) \\
\text{Design variables : } \boldsymbol{\eta}_p, f_p(t_j) &\quad (p = 1, 2, \dots, N_P; j = 1, 2, \dots, J)
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where $\| \cdot \|$ denotes the Euclidean norm, w is a large constant, $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside step function, d_{pq} is the distance between the coating p th and q th point impacts, and

$$\bar{\xi}_i^* = \left[\xi_i^*(t_1) \quad \xi_i^*(t_2) \quad \dots \quad \xi_i^*(t_J) \right]^T \tag{16}$$

$$\mathbf{A}_i = \begin{bmatrix} a_i(1, 1) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ a_i(1, 2) & a_i(2, 2) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ a_i(1, J) & a_i(2, J) & \dots & a_i(J, J) \end{bmatrix} \tag{17}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{ip} = \left[\boldsymbol{\phi}_i^T \boldsymbol{\eta}_p f_p(t_1) \quad \boldsymbol{\phi}_i^T \boldsymbol{\eta}_p f_p(t_2) \quad \dots \quad \boldsymbol{\phi}_i^T \boldsymbol{\eta}_p f_p(t_J) \right]^T \tag{18}$$

By solving the optimization problem of Eq.(15), the optima of $\boldsymbol{\eta}_p$ ($p = 1, 2, \dots, N_P$) and $f_p(t_j)$ ($p = 1, 2, \dots, N_P; j = 1, 2, \dots, J$) are obtained, that is, the locations and the force histories of the multiple point impacts are identified.

In order to solve the optimization problem of Eq. (15), we use the genetic algorithm (GA) for searching the optima of $\boldsymbol{\eta}_p$ ($p = 1, 2, \dots, N_P$) and the gradient projection method with golden section method for searching the optima of $f_p(t_j)$ ($p = 1, 2, \dots, N_P; j = 1, 2, \dots, J$). The GA is also used to solve the optimization problem of Eq. (13), when discrete values are assigned for \mathbf{Q}_r and \mathbf{T}_r .

RESULTS OF IDENTIFICATION AND DISCUSSION

Numerical examples of identification are treated for the rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel which is made of a $[45_4/0_8/-45_4/90_4]_s$ CFRP composite laminated plate and a unidirectional CFRP composite isogrid, and the rectangular composite sandwich panel which is made of $[0/90/45/-45]_s$ CFRP composite face sheets and an aluminum honeycomb core. The dimensions of the rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel are $L = 824.4$ mm, $W = 634.6$ mm, $h^s = 5$ mm and $h^s = 15$ mm, and those of the rectangular composite sandwich panel are $L = 1000$ mm, $W = 750$ mm, $h^f = 1$ mm and $h^c = 10$ mm.

(a) Composite isogrid-stiffened panel.

(b) Composite sandwich panel.

Fig. 2 Locations of strain measurement positions.

(i) Impact location.

(i) Impact location.

(ii) Impact force history.

(ii) Impact force history.

(a) Composite isogrid-stiffened panel.

(b) Composite sandwich panel.

Fig. 3 Identification results of the location and force history of a single point impact.

In the numerical examples of identification, we use the following measured longitudinal strains:

$$\varepsilon_{Lr}^*(t_k) = \varepsilon_{Lr}^{\text{EXACT}}(t_k) + \varepsilon_{Lr}^{\text{MAX}} \times \frac{S}{100} \times R \quad (r = 1, 2, \dots, N_R; k = 1, 2, \dots, J) \quad (19)$$

where $\varepsilon_{Lr}^{\text{EXACT}}(t_k)$ are the longitudinal strains at the locations of strain measurement positions, which are obtained by the direct three-dimensional finite element analysis, $\varepsilon_{Lr}^{\text{MAX}}$ the maxima of $\varepsilon_{Lr}^{\text{EXACT}}$ in the time period of impact, S a range of measurement error and R a uniform random number in the range from -1 to 1. In this study, S is set at $S = 5$. The measured longitudinal strains $\varepsilon_{Lr}^*(t_k)$ are provided at the time intervals of $50 \mu\text{s}$, and the impact forces at the same time intervals are identified in the time period of 10 ms. The largest mode number M is set at $M = 50$.

We examine first the identification results of the location and force history of a single point impact acting perpendicularly on the rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel and the rectangular composite sandwich panel. The identification is performed using the measured longitudinal strains at the locations of 25 strain measurement positions shown

(i) Impact locations.

(i) Impact locations.

(ii) Impact force histories.

(ii) Impact force histories.

(a) Composite isogrid-stiffened panel.

(b) Composite sandwich panel.

Fig. 4 Identification results of the locations and force histories of two point impacts.

in Fig. 2. In the figure, the dot marks with a short line denote the strain measurement positions. The short line indicates the direction of longitudinal strain.

Fig. 3 depicts the identification results of the location and force history of the single point impact. In the figure, the marks \circ and \times denote, respectively, the identification result of impact location and the exact location, and the dark spot and the solid line denote, respectively, the identification result of impact force history and the exact force history. As can be seen from Fig. 3, the identification results of impact location and impact force history are in good agreement with the exact ones.

Let us proceed to the identification of the locations and force histories of multiple point impacts acting perpendicularly on the rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel and the rectangular composite sandwich panel. The identification is performed for two and three point impacts using the measured longitudinal strains at the same locations of 25 strain measurement positions as shown in Fig. 2, when the maximum number of coating multiple point impacts is set at $N_p = 2$ and 3, respectively. Fig. 4 depicts the identification results of the locations and force histories of two point impacts denoted by A and B, and

Fig. 5 Identification results of the locations and force histories of three point impacts.

Fig. 5 depicts the identification results of the locations and force histories of three point impacts denoted by A, B and C. Figs. 4 and 5 reveal that the identification results of impact locations and impact force histories are consistent with the exact ones and the detection of the multiple point impacts is valid.

CONCLUSIONS

We have been concerned with the detection of multiple point impacts on composite structural panels using measured longitudinal strain responses. The impact locations and impact force histories have been identified in such a manner that the modal coordinates are adjusted to the measured modal coordinates. We have examined first the identification results of the location and force history of the single point impact acting on the rectangular composite isogrid-stiffened panel and the rectangular composite sandwich panel. After the examination, the locations and force histories of the multiple point impacts have been identified. By comparing the identification results of impact locations and impact force histories with the exact ones, it has been found that the identification results and the exact ones are consistent, and the validity of the detection of multiple point impacts has been verified.

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